

Derivatives of 1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid. Part II. 4-Halogeno-1-methoxy-2-naphthoic Acids and their Derivatives.

BY G. V. JADHAV AND S. N. RAO.

In continuation of our work (Jadhav, Rao and Hirwe, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 609) the methyl ethers of 4-halogeno-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids are studied in this paper. The methylation of these acids by the usual method of dimethylsulphate in alkaline solution being unsuccessful, 1-methoxy-2-naphthoic acid was halogenated. This behaviour of the 4-halogeno-naphthoic acids compares well with the 3:5-disubstituted salicylic acids.

The methyl ether of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid was prepared according to Froelicher and Cohen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 1654) by methylating methyl 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoate. The yield of the ester has been considerably improved by obtaining it through 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoyl chloride (Anschutz, Weber and Runkel, *Annalen*, 1906, **346**, 361). The methoxy acid was halogenated and the constitution of the halogeno acids confirmed by demethylating them to the corresponding 4-halogeno-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid (Jadhav, Rao and Hirwe, *loc. cit.*). Various derivatives of these acids have been described.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methyl 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoate.—To 1-hydroxy-1-naphthoyl chloride (from 20 g. of the hydroxy acid) methyl alcohol (40 c.c.) was slowly added and the ester obtained (15 g.) crystallised from rectified spirit as pale yellow needles, m.p. 77-78° (Schmitt and Burkard, *Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 2700; Cohen and Dudley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **97**, 1747).

4-Bromo-1-methoxy-2-naphthoic Acid.—Bromine (10 g.) in acetic acid (40 c.c.) was slowly added with stirring to 1-methoxy-2-naphthoic acid (10 g.), prepared by the method of Froelicher and Cohen (*loc. cit.*), in acetic acid (70 c.c.). The bromo acid (12-13 g.), which slowly separated out, crystallised from rectified spirit as white shining needles, m. p. 196-97°. (Found: Br, 28.2. $C_{12}H_9O_3Br$ requires Br, 28.5 per cent).

Demethylation of 4-Bromo-1-methoxy-2-naphthoic Acid.—Acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) was slowly added to a mixture of the bromomethoxy acid (0.5 g.) and hydroiodic acid (*d* 1.5, 5 c.c.), and the mixture heated at 100° for 1 hour. This mixture was treated with water and the solid obtained crystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m. p. 239-40° (decomp.), mixed m. p. with an authentic sample of 4-bromo-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid.

4-Bromo-1-methoxy-2-naphthoic Chloride.—A mixture of the bromomethoxy acid (3 g.), dry light petroleum ether (12 c.c.), dry benzene (3 c.c.) and phosphorus pentachloride (3 g.) was gently heated on the water-bath, until a clear solution was obtained. On cooling the naphthoic chloride separated in white needles, which were filtered and washed with dry light petroleum ether and dried over phosphorus pentoxide, m. p. 114-15°. [Found: Total halogen calc. as Cl, 27.7; (by analysis of silver halides), Cl, 12.0, Br, 27.1. $C_{12}H_8O_2BrCl$ requires Cl, 11.9; Br, 26.7 per cent).

4-Chloro-1-methoxy-2-naphthoic Acid.—Dry chlorine gas (3.5 g.) was passed into a mixture of 1-methoxy-2-naphthoic acid (10 g.) in acetic acid (150 c.c.). The separated solid (7 g.) crystallised from rectified spirit in white shining needles, m. p. 182-83°. (Found: Cl, 14.8. $C_{12}H_8O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 15.0 per cent).

The constitution of the chloromethoxy acid was proved in the same way as its bromo isomer by demethylating it to 4-chloro-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid, m.p. 231-32° (decomp.).

4-Chloro-1-methoxy-2-naphthoic Chloride was prepared in the same way as its bromo isomer; white needles, m.p. 106-7°. (Found: Cl, 27.8. $C_{12}H_8O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 27.9 per cent).

The phenyl and β -naphthyl esters of the 4-halogeno-1-methoxy-2-naphthoic acids were prepared by heating a mixture of the halogeno acid with the respective phenol and phosphorus oxychloride at 110-20° to a clear solution and the ester obtained on treating it with water.

The alkyl esters were obtained by heating either the silver salt of the acid or the naphthoic chloride with the respective alkyl iodide or alcohol.

The arylamides were obtained by treating a benzene solution of the naphthoic chloride with the respective amine.

TABLE I.

Derivatives of 4-Bromo-1-methoxy-2-naphthoic Acid.

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Name.	Formula.	Crystallised from.	Appearance.	M.p.	Found.	Analysis.	Calc.
Phenyl ester	$C_{17}H_{15}O_3Br$	Alcohol	White shining needles	88-89°	Br, 22.5%		22.4%
β -Naphthyl ester	$C_{21}H_{19}O_3Br$	Acetic acid	Small white needles	114-15°	19.7		19.7
Ethyl ester	$C_{11}H_{13}O_3Br$	Alcohol	White needles	78-79°	26.2		25.9
Methyl ester	$C_{10}H_{11}O_3Br$	"	Pinkish needles	96-97°	27.2		27.1
Anilide	$C_{18}H_{17}O_2NBr$	"	White needles	123-24°	Br, 22.7 N (micro), 4.0		22.5 3.9
<i>o</i> -Toluidide	$C_{19}H_{17}O_2NBr$	Acetic acid	White plates	142-43°	Br, 21.6		21.6
<i>m</i> -Toluidide	" "	Alcohol	White needles	122-23°	21.6		21.6
<i>p</i> -Toluidide	" "	"	"	143-44°	21.9		21.6

TABLE II.
Derivatives of 4-Chloro-1-methoxy-2-naphthoic Acid.

Name.	Formula.	Crystallised from.	Appearance.	M.P.	Found.	Analysis, Calc.
Phenyl ester	$C_{13}H_{13}O_3Cl$	Alcohol	White needles	74-75°	Cl, 11.2%	11.4%
<i>β</i> -Naphthyl ester	$C_{17}H_{15}O_3Cl$	Acetic acid	"	112-13°	10.0	9.8
Ethyl ester	$C_{14}H_{15}O_3Cl$	Alcohol	Small white needles	77-78°	13.2	13.4
Methyl ester	$C_{13}H_{11}O_3Cl$	"	White needles	83-84°	14.1	14.2
Amide	$C_{13}H_{14}O_2NCl$	"	Shining white needles	105.6°	Cl, 11.4 N (micro), 4.6	11.4 4.5
<i>o</i> -Toluidide	$C_{14}H_{16}O_2NCl$	"	Thick needles	134-35°	Cl, 11.1	10.9
<i>m</i> -Toluidide	"	"	White shining needles	116-17°	11.1	10.9
<i>p</i> -Toluidide	"	"	Small white needles	113-14°	11.0	10.9

The micro analyses were carried out by Dr. J. N. Ray of Lahore.
 The authors thank Dr. T. S. Wheeler and Mr. N. W. Hirwe for their keen interest in the work.